

Proverbs and their functions

Baltabaeva Gulimxon
Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasi,
Qo'ng'iro't tumani, 37-maktab
ingliz tili o'qituvchisi

Annotation: *The article gives information about the proverbs, their history, linguistic functions and classification, as well as characteristics and features. The author provides some proverbs with their translations in three languages: English, Russian and Uzbek to discover their cultural aspects to the readers.*

Key words: proverbs, sayings, cultural aspects, linguistic, nationality, reflect, features, classification, folklore etc.

Proverbs are works that summarize the wise and prudent expressions of the people, the words of great cultural figures, scientists, statesmen, the wise thoughts of the individuals based on their life experience. Proverbs are considered as simple, brief, concrete, traditional saying that expresses perceived truth based on common sense or experience. Proverbs are often metaphorical and utilize formulaic language. Collectively, they form a genre of folklore. The ideas of proverbs are clear, the conclusions are complete, the expressions are concise, and of course the sentences are exemplary. Proverbs have a poetic and prose structure. They reflect diligence, patriotism, courage, generosity, justice, honesty, friendship, nobility, sincere human ideas, pure love, the call to knowledge, and so on.

Proverbs are words of wisdom, and they were first heard of in Egypt soon after 3000 B.C. About 600 years later a vizier by the name of Ptah-hotep attained high repute for his wisdom. His precepts, in the form of a collection of proverbial sayings, were preserved and are claimed to be the oldest book in the world. They comprise a sort of ethical treatise that assumes the nature of the good life and undertakes to tell how this can be realized by the special group for whom it was written. Wisdom speculation arose also in Babylonia, where other writers composed bodied of proverbs or pessimistic writings that denied any value in life.

This intellectual activity could not have been confined to a few favored lands. Even uncivilized peoples ask and answer questions about the nature of the world and the meaning of human life, and such speculation is universal among more advanced cultures. And so wisdom was pervasive through the ancient east. The little land of Edom was famous for its wise men, and apparently there was a wisdom movement among the Canaanites before the Hebrews entered Palestine.

It is no accident that the Greek word "philosophy" means "love of wisdom", that is of "knowledge". The full measure of Greece's debt to the orient has never been determined, but in any case Greek philosophy was heir to and in some measure disciple of the age-old speculation of the east. Yet wisdom was both more and less than philosophy. Much that is now included under the term had not then risen above the intellectual horizon, but also much that then was wisdom later attained an independent position.

Proverbs are probably the oldest extant documents of the Hebrew wisdom movement, of which King Solomon was the founder and patron. Wisdom literature flourished throughout the ancient Near East, with Egyptian examples dating back to before the middle of the 3rd millennium B.C. It revolved around the professional sages, or wise men, and scribes in the service of the court, and consisted primarily in maxims about the practical, intelligent way to conduct one's life and in speculations about the very worth and meaning of human life. The most common form of these wise sayings, which were intended for oral instruction especially in the schools run by the sages for the young men at the court, was the *marshal* (Hebrew: "comparison" or "parable," although frequently translated "proverb"). Typically a pithy, easily memorized aphoristic saying based on experience and universal in application, the *marshal* in its simplest and oldest form was a couplet in which a definition was given in two parallel lines related to each other either antithetically or synthetically.

The practical shrewdness of the businessman and administrator, incipient science, general knowledge, reflection upon known facts and much else of the sort, as well as more strictly philosophic speculation, went into the total of wisdom. The educated men, particularly if he gave thought to human conduct and its ends, was the wise man. Wisdom was the total of the intellectual culture of the age. And to end a very serious thinking, I would say that wisdom is strictly connected with culture, that is the pragmatic knowledge to solve real problems of life and explain or suppose new theories for our poor existence.

Literary and culturally speaking, proverbs are also very near to parable that can make difficult concepts easier to understand, since they are exemplified stories as we can read in the moral and spiritual tales of Buddha, Jesus and many others. Proverbs were often appended to Aesop's fables as a way to sum up and re-enforce the meaning of the story. As a matter of fact, if parables are metaphors in story form, then proverbs are parables in miniature. Like parables proverbs contain great metaphors that can teach us good moral lessons, they usually express the wit of one for the wisdom of many.

Proverbs, again like parables, are found in every country and culture, and they are very close to aphorisms, as the world oldest written art form. In ancient Sumer, where writing itself was invented around 3500 B.C., proverbs were used as textbooks for moral instruction and many of them anticipates contemporary sayings, such as this one: "Wealth is hard to come by, but poverty is always at hand", that later becomes: "The poor are always with us." Obviously even though proverbs are universal, the metaphorical images through which they tell their stories vary, providing this way visualized cultural nuances for the different readers.

That's why we can find a lot of lovers of all form of proverbs and parables, and this is also the reason why books like the Bible, the works of Shakespeare, or Aesop's Fables or Pilgrim's Progress by John Bunyan are so famous in the English and world literature, and they can teach people of lot, as Abraham Lincoln through his speeches and writing has always demonstrated. Parables and proverbs are the foundations of religious, moral, wisdom and sapiential literature and they are very popular in folk literature as well, also because they convey spiritual truths setting them aside with natural truths.

Proverbs like aphorism are short saying that states sometimes a general truth or more often something else, they use all the different rhetoric figures and can give us a lot of definitions, metaphors, moral teachings, observations, and can help us create and develop

more thoughts or pensée. They can act as an inspiration and serve as a practical guide to living a better and more conscious life. Many maxims are anonymous and not a few echo ancient proverbs.

The best known collection of proverbs is The Book of Proverbs which follows The Psalms in the Old Testament. This Bible Book is a collection of ancient wisdom that uses a form of Hebrew poetry unfamiliar to us because it doesn't rhyme, and it is still recognized today as full of practical advice. Like the wisdom sayings in the Book of Proverbs, all other pieces of this short and extremely condensed literature of varying provenience are composed in poetic form, that is, they are cast in parallelisms, that Herder praised as a form of "thought rhyme" literature.

The Book of Proverbs contains the sayings not only of Solomon, but other sages of ancient Israel as well. The teachings of this book can be applied by everyone from children to young men and women to the leaders of business empires and nations. There are no teachings in it that are peculiar to Israel, but instead, Proverbs contains truths that apply universally to all of human kind. It contains warnings, admonitions, standards of conduct and speech, revelation and promises. Our modern world would profit greatly if more of us would read and apply what Proverbs teaches. Proverbs are highly compressed, carefully chosen words of wisdom and in the Bible, they are found elsewhere than just in the Book of Proverbs.

Proverbs of other culture are always fascinating and sometimes very difficult to understand. They are common to most cultures and ages, because they represent homely wisdom, transmitted orally in the ancient past and through different books in modern times, since they are very similar to aphorisms, apothegms, and maxims.

Here are some examples: *Send a fool to close the shutters and he'll close them all over the town* (Yiddish); *You cannot step twice into the same river* (Classical Greek); *When you want a drink of milk you don't buy the cow* (Cretan); *If vinegar is free it is sweeter than honey* (Serbian); *An uninvited guest is worse than a Tatar* (Russian); *There is but an hour a day between a good housewife and a bad one* (English); *It is better to wear out one's shoes than one's sheets* (Genoese); *The wife carries her husband on her face, the husband carries the wife on his linen* (Bulgarian); *Watch the faces of those who bow low* (Polish); *If it is not in the head it is in the feet* (Czech); *Visits always give pleasure – if not the arrival, the departure* (Portuguese); *To tell a woman what she may not do is to tell her what she can* (Spanish); *Every invalid is a physician* (Irish). A fine collection of English proverbs is the Oxford Dictionary of English Proverbs.

Functions and Classifications of Proverbs

There are many functions of proverbs: to advice, inspire, teach, persuade, convince, etc. Most proverbs are of an instructional character and provide deep philosophic insight into many phenomena of life. Proverbs guide people, teach them to differentiate between right and wrong, to lead a regular life, to establish good relations with the community members: *Better die with honor than live with shame; When the blind lead the blind, both shall fall into the ditch; Better be an old man's darling, than a young man's slave; Where there is a will, there is a way; The early bird catches the worm; Love is not found in the market; A woman's work is never done; Better to have loved and lost, than never to have loved at all; What can't be cured must be endured; One man's meat is another man's poison.*

Some proverbs reveal and criticize people's negative characteristics: *the fox changes his*

skin, but not his habit; a leopard cannot change its spots; like father, like son.

Many proverbs summarize knowledge and experience of people's daily life: *The best wine comes out of an old vessel; Soft fire makes sweet malt; Hunger drives the wolf out of the woods; Don't count your chickens before they are hatched; All that glitters is not gold; If you play with fire you get burnt; You buy land, you buy stones; You buy meat, you buy bones.* (D.U. Ashurova, M.R. Galieva)

As proverbs are devoted to various topics, we can divide them into classifications and functions to categorize them with their special names. Various categorizations of proverbs have been proposed by different scholars. The classifications of proverbs are as follows:

- 1) the peculiarities of lifestyle;
 - 2) geographical position;
 - 3) customs and traditions;
 - 4) religious views;
 - 5) Greek and Roman myths;
 - 6) English literature;
 - 7) historical events.
- (D.U. Ashurova, M.R. Galieva).

One typical advantages of classifying the proverbs is developing communication on these areas.

1. Proverbs reflecting the peculiarities of lifestyle.

Wherever people are alive, there are communicating process. Proverbs can be one of the most effective tool of enriching language. A lot of proverbs are connected with individuals' lifestyle and working process. An enormous number of proverbs were created by working people such as seamen, hunters, farmers, workmen, housewives cooks guests and so on. For instance: (D.U. Ashurova, M.R. Galieva).

№	English proverbs	Russian proverbs	Uzbek proverbs	The proverbs are for:
1	A bad workman quarrels his tools.	Плохой плясун всегда музыканта.	O'zolmagan otga o'zagi bahona.	Unprofessional individuals /lazy people
2	Welcome is the best cheer.	Принес Бог гостя, дал хозяину пир.	Mehmon izzatda-Mezbon xizmatda.	Guests/hosts
3	Living without the aim is like sailing without a compass.	Жизнь без цели-пустая жизнь.	Bo'sh qor- tik turmas.	Aimless people
4	If you run after two hares, you will catch neither.	За двумя зайцами погонишься, ни одного не поймаешь.	Ikki kemani boshini ushlagan-suvga g'arq bo'lur.	For individuals who are trying to finish their some tasks in a parallel way.
5	Too many cooks spoil the broth.	У семи нянек дитя без глазу.	1.Shakarning ham ozi yaxshi. 2.Har narsaning me'yori yaxshi.	For individuals who are expected to pay attention to the quality of working, not quantity.

2. Proverbs expressing geographical location of the country.

: The words *Sea* and *Ocean* are used in many countries cultures as proverbs. We can get some information about those nationalities, their life-styles, history as well as traditions. Here are some countries proverbs which related to the words *Sea* and *Ocean*:

	Proverbs	Nationalities
1	Little leaks sink in the ship	English
2	The sea refuses no river.	English
3	A smooth sea never makes a skillful mariner	English
4	He who would catch fish must not mind getting wet	English
5	The sea becomes the shore, the shore becomes the sea.	Indonesian
6	The boat sails by, the shore remains.	Cambodian
7	One can not scoop up the ocean with a sea shell.	Japanese
8	You can often find in rivers what you can not find in oceans.	Traditional proverb
9	Seamen learn to get to know each other during a storm.	Corsican
10	Do good and throw it in the sea.	Palestinian
11	Do not look for a sea when you can drown in a puddle.	Russian
12	The frog in his pond sneers at the ocean.	Japanese.
13	Do not sell the fish that is still swimming in the ocean.	Turkish
14	A wreck on shore is a beacon at sea.	Traditional
15	He who wants pearls has to dive into the sea.	Kurdish
16	When husband and wife live in harmony, they can dry up the ocean without a bucket.	Vietnamese.

17	Smooth seas do not make skillful sailors.	African
18	Though near shore, you're still in the ocean.	Malawian
19	Better poor on land than rich at sea.	Dutch
20	It is safest to sail within reach of the shore.	Dutch
21	Love begins with song and music and ends in a sea of tears.	Italian
22	When the sea turned into honey, the beggar lost his spoon.	Bulgarian
23	Man is like a bubble of water on the ocean.	Italian
24	The river's reputation ends where the sea begins.	Russian
25	With money you can build a road in the sea.	Maltese
26	Foam will always find its way to the shore.	Solomon Islander
27	Praise the sea but keep on land.	English
28	God will help a seaman in storm but the pilot must still remain at the wheel.	German
29	A man with little learning is like the frog who thinks its pond is an ocean.	Myanmar
30	A ship on the beach is a lighthouse to the sea.	Dutch
31	The existence of the sea means the existence of pirates.	Malay
32	If rain bothers you, you can always jump into the sea.	Chinese
33	The water is a deep sea between saying and doing	Italian
34	The urine of one dog will not pollute the ocean	French

3. Proverbs reflecting customs and traditions.

Cultural proverbs and sayings provide an insightful window into a community's lifestyle, history and culture. Passed on from generation to generation, much of it through oral culture, proverbs are still widely used today and have become a part of everyday speech. They are generally applied to reinforce arguments, illustrate ideas, and deliver messages of wisdom, inspiration, consolation, celebration and guidance.

№	Proverbs	Nationalities
1	If you want to go fast, go alone. If you want to go far, go together	African
2	Fall seven times, stand up eight.	Japanese.
3	Shared joy is a double joy, shared sorrow is half a sorrow.	Swedish.

4	Words should be weighed, not counted.	Yiddish
5	If you can't live longer, live deeper.	Italian
6	A man who uses force is afraid of reasoning,	Kenyan
7	Still waters run deep.	Latin
8	He who does not travel, does not know the value of men.	Moorish
9	Measure a thousand times and cut ones.	Turkish
10	A spoon does not know the taste of soup, nor a learned fool the taste of wisdom.	Welsh
11	The most beautiful fig may contain a worm.	Zulu.
12	Change yourself and fortune will change.	Portuguese
13	In love, there is always one who kisses and one who offers the check.	French.
14	Who begins too much, accomplishes little.	German.
15	Whoever gossips to you will gossip about you.	Spanish
16	Beauty lies in the eye of the beholder.	English
17	Don't sail out farther than you can row back.	Danish
18	Age is honorable and youth is noble.	Irish
19	If you take big paces, you leave big spaces.	Burmese

4. Proverbs reflecting religious views.

Proverbs is a book about how followers of God can live alongside others with integrity and put their faith into action. It shows how a relationship with God can permeate every action and thought.

As is known, Christianity is a dominant religion in English-speaking countries and therefore the Bible, a sacred book of all Christians, became the richest source of English proverbs. It is believed that European cultures are greatly influenced by the Bible. Consequently, many sayings and quotes from the Bible have taken deep roots in people's consciousness; however, their origin has been forgotten. Here, some examples: *If the blind lead the blind, both shall fall into the ditch*, *Forbidden fruit is sweetest*, (D.U. Ashurova, M.R. Galieva).

5. Proverbs originated from Greek and Roman myths.

Many English proverbs originate from Greek and Roman myths, i.e. fabulous stories about the world creation and destruction, gods and heroes, their deeds, victories and defeats. These myths are well known in all European countries, in particular English-speaking countries, because they were a part of education and art (paintings, sculptures, books): *The Devil too has Achilles' heel*; *Not even Hercules could contend against two*; *Without Ceres and Bacchus, Venus grows cold*.

Many English proverbs are also taken from The Fables of Aesop. These proverbs are very concise and humorous, and they reflect people's life experience. For example: *The camel going to seek horns, lost his ears*; *The grapes are sour*; *A barleycorn is better than a diamond to a cock*; *One swallow does not make a summer*; *Slow but sure wins the race*; *Kill not the goose that lays the golden eggs*. (D.U. Ashurova, M.R. Galieva).

6. proverbs originated from English literature

Many English proverbs reflect events or characters of English literature. Shakespeare's works are undoubtedly the greatest literary source of many English proverbs. The English use Shakespeare's quotes not realizing their origin, for example: *All is not gold that glitters; Patience performe is medicine for a mad dog; Brevity is the soul of wit; Sweet are the uses of adversity; Cowards die many times before their deaths.*

There are proverbs from other literary sources as well: *A little learning is a dangerous thing* (Pope); *Knowledge is power* (Bacon); *A thing of beauty is a joy forever* (Keats). (D.U. Ashurova, M.R. Galieva).

7. proverbs borrowed from other languages

The processes of the world integration and globalization stipulate the development of linguistic contracts, which, in turn, have a certain influence on the language system in general, and lexical and phraseological subsystems in particular. It is evidenced by a great number of borrowings from one language to others. As for proverbs, they are also subjected to this tendency, therefore a lot of proverbs were borrowed from other languages, including Greek, Latin, German, Italian, Spanish, Dutch and other languages, among which Latin, Greek and French provide the richest nutrition. Most of the borrowed proverbs in English, due to the remoteness of time, have already assimilated or merged into the English language with their traces almost impossible to follow.

Many English proverbs originated from French due to the historical facts. William, Duke of Normandy, France, landed his mighty army and defeated Saxon king Harold. William was crowned as king of England, and extended French culture, language and architecture in Britain. The conquerors had been ruling England for a long period of time, and French used to be an official language. Although England finally won its sovereignty, many French proverbs remained: *Don't put the cart before the horse; Venture a small fish to catch a great one; If the lion's skin cannot, the fox's shall.*

Many English proverbs are of Latin origin, because firstly Britain used to be a part of the Roman Empire for some time; secondly Christianity was introduced in Latin and thirdly the influence of the Renaissance. Many Latin words and proverbs gained wide acceptance in English culture: *Fortune favors the brave; He who says what he likes, shall hear what he does not like; I fear the Greeks, even when bringing gifts; There is no rule without an exception.*

It is necessary to mention that a number of proverbs in English borrowed from Latin and French have remained more common in their original form rather than in translations: *In vino veritas* (Latin); *Honi soit qui mal* (French); *Caveat emptor* (Latin). (D.U. Ashurova, M.R. Galieva).

The characteristics and features of Proverbs

Every proverb values or appreciates any event both positively and negatively. Such kind of features serve to make the proverbs popular among people. Proverbs express wise and complete idea and sayings express the description of something but do not give complete meanings. They consist of one compositional element.

Proverbs can be used in neutral figurative meaning. This features of proverbs widen the sphere of their usage thematically. That's why proverbs are famous among different nations and people. Sayings are characterized by limited usage in one or two nations who are near

to each other geographically and in non related languages. In spite of their own specific features proverbs have general sides which also belong to the other types of folklore. One of such features of the proverbs is that they are created in language in a very long time and disappear in a long period. It is connected with the formal feature of the content of the proverb.

To turn some wise thoughts into proverbs some conditions are required. And this conditions may be the followings:

Firstly, the proverbs should describe the economic, social and politic life of the people.

Secondary, the idea expressed in the proverb must have global character. It means that those proverbs that describe the characters related to the human beings are the same in all the languages.

Thirdly, the idea that can be used as sample and answers to the above conditions must be complete in literary Christianized form. When the pattern idea answers these three questions it turns to be a proverb. Also it should be pointed out that the character of immediate creation of proverbs are connected with sociable structure, the dominance and non dominance of politic, cultural, social - economic life. The content expressed in proverb changes depending on the change in social life.

Proverbs serve as rare base in researching or studying of people: the level of their cultural, politic, economic life in ancient time or periods. As proverbs reflect the life practice of people over different periods and also they reflect moral norms and religious faith of nation. One more feature of proverbs is that proverbs are often used in colloquial speech of people and are extended in varied forms. As we know, proverbs are used for some practical, pragmatic purposes in various circumstances of everyday communication. It is not right to consider proverbs apart from pragmatic functions. As to familiar quotations, they are different from proverbs in their origin. They come from literature and many people using them do not even know that they are quoting and very few could accurately name the play or passage on which they are drawing even when they are aware of using a quotation from Shakespeare: *For example: Something is rotten in the state of Denmark; Brevity is the soul of wit.*

To conclude, Proverbs are a part of a language and closely integrated with the society and culture. They not only represent a kind of cultural phenomenon, but also record culture and its development. They cannot exist out of culture. Proverbs can provide interesting clues to people, geography, history, social organization, social views and attitudes and they have great cultural values. For this reason, proverbs are culture-specific. Language and culture are highly integrated with each other. It is generally acknowledged that language and culture are inseparable and mutually influenced. Therefore, it is important for a language learner to learn proverbs to understand or appreciate it. Moreover, learning proverbs will enrich the learners' knowledge and use of the language. Therefore, it is worth to do the research on proverbs.

References:

1. Carl William Brown (An article from the site)
2. D.U. Ashurova. M.R. Galieva (Cultural Linguistic book).
3. Hoe Rong (Article. Proverbs reveal Culture Diversity).
- 4 Kanat Sydyakov “Contrastive studies on Proverbs”)
5. Mieder. W (2004) (“Proverbs”).
6. Dahl V.I (2003). (Russian Proverbs)